

Managing Classroom Using Real-life Experience: The concept of Freedom in Learning Implementation

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ABSTRACT: Teaching-learning activities involve various elements, such as classroom management. Learning approach is a way for teachers to manage the class because it assists them in learning activity. This study was qualitative study using data obtained from documentation and observation. Score average and percentage were employed as research technique to determine the correlation between learning approach in classroom management and learning success. This study aims to find out how real-life experience can be used as learning approach in managing art class. Accordingly, the results indicated that implementing a real-life experience-based approach in managing art classes showed a positive but insignificant effect. It seen from good category (an average of 3.00-3.75) and midterm scores that show 52.9% scored higher than 65 (passing mark), while 47.1% scored less than 65. It indicates although the approach had positive influence, it was not significant in improving students' results.

KEYWORDS: Arts education, Classroom management, Freedom in learning, Real-life-based learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning activities are a process of transferring knowledge to students in order to achieve learning objectives (Popham and Baker 2008; Handayani 2013). These activities include preparing lesson plans, presenting materials, presenting media or teaching aids, providing evaluations, and providing follow-up learning (Popham and Baker 2008; Mansor et al. 2012; Osman 2013). Classroom management is one of the important aspects of the teaching and learning process because it greatly influences the success of achieving learning objectives (Sims et al. 2022). In fact, the purpose of classroom management is to create a classroom situation and condition an effective learning environment so as to enable students to learn and develop their abilities to the fullest (Rukmana and Suryana 2006; Watkins 2008; Yamin and Maisah 2009; Mansor et al. 2012). Classroom management needs to be done because this activity can be effective, direct, and significant in influencing the success of learning (Wehby, and Reschly 2011; Parsonson 2012; Oliver, Broome 2013). This happens because this activity has a function to control and create a good learning environment by dampening and solving problems in teaching and learning activities (Oliver and Reschly 2007; Akin-Little, Little, and Laniti 2007; Raslinda 2021). One form of classroom management is the selection of appropriate learning strategies and approaches for teaching and learning activities. This opinion is consistent with previous studies which stated that there is a correlation between student learning success and the selection of appropriate learning approaches and strategies (Oliver and Reschly 2007; Meiers 2008; Oliver, Wehby, and Reschly 2011; Zein 2018; Özen and Yildirim 2020; Badamas 2021).

There have been various changes in the development of education. Since ancient times, the initial concept of education has never changed; it was to liberate human beings both physically and mentally through knowledge (Hopkins 1976; Unesco 2007). Over time, this concept remains similar, without any significant changes, but it only adapts to the needs of the times (Specia and Osman 2015; Hinchliffe 2018). Corresponding to the changing and the development of the era, the concept of education offered another thought, which was the freedom of learning (Specia and Osman 2015; Hinchliffe 2018; Maisyaroh et al. 2021). This thought came from the idea to eliminate the inequality of learning (Dewey 1997; 2015) which has been commonly found in many educational institutions and systems (Hopkins 1976; Osman 2013). In Freirean Critical pedagogy (Freire 2005), educational institutions are described as places where emancipation takes place. In reality, this idea was rarely found as it mostly focused on one side, namely teachers and institutions, but ignored the students (serving as passive objects or recipients) who actually lay on another side (Forte 2009; Ozer 2013; Council of Europe 2015). According to Burbules and Berk (1999), critical pedagogy is an attempt to work within educational institutions and systems to question the inequalities existing in the institutions. Accordingly, López-Gopar and Sughrua (2014) argued that critical pedagogy allows students to discuss and express individual thoughts. In addition, critical pedagogy corresponds to the idea brought by (Dewey 1997; 2015) and (Hooks 2010) regarding freedom in learning as well as academic freedom

(Osman 2013). The thought of freedom of learning later became the basis for the independent education system adopted in Indonesia which was known as "Merdeka Belajar". This education system proposed flexibility to education actors (teachers and students) to determine individual learning system that suits their needs. This education system is considered appropriate to deal with the changing of the times where each differs from another in terms of the need for knowledge (Hopkins 1976; Mujtahidin, Oktariato, and Afriyadi 2021; Maisyaroh et al. 2021). Furthermore, this opinion is supported by previous studies, which prove the suitability of this education system in facing the challenges of the 4.0 era (Mujtahidin, Oktariato, and Afriyadi 2021; Maisyaroh et al. 2021).

Arts education has an important role in optimizing the potential of students. One aspect developed through art education is creative intelligence. Marshal and D'Adamo (2011) and Mephah (2015) stated that art can develop ways of thinking, including creative ways of thinking. Arts education can evoke creative responses and personal ideas (Nilson, Fetherston, and McMurray 2014). In art education, the learning activities carried out do not only focus on theoretical knowledge but also emphasize practical knowledge (Nilson et al. 2013). This is because the purpose of learning in arts education is to ensure students gain knowledge and information which can then be practically implemented in real life (Mephah 2015). From these objectives, arts education actors (especially teachers as class managers) should be able to design an appropriate learning system in order to achieve the targeted objectives. Therefore, selecting the appropriate learning model or approach for teaching-learning activities in the classroom becomes one of the main concerns in arts education (Broome 2013; Mephah 2015; Jamagh, Al-Muttalabi, and Samari 2021).

Research and studies on using real-life experiences in teaching and learning activities have been carried out for the past few years (Powell 2015; Noobanjong and Louhapensang 2017; Kinberg 2020). One of them is by inviting practitioners (researchers, teachers, or people who are active in writing in journals) as the source and informants in learning academic writing to share their writing experiences (Kinberg 2020). It was because they were able to provide a concrete picture of the problems or issues that possibly occur and were faced by learners while doing a similar activity (Kinberg 2020). In contrast to conventional learning, real-life experience-based learning is a model, strategy, or learning approach that uses real experience both from the learner himself and from other people who act as sources (Andresen, Boud, and Cohen 1995; Kolb and Kolb 2017; Abuhassna et al. 2021). This learning approach allows learners to create or gain new knowledge or understanding from information or knowledge provided by sources (Ferry et al. 2012; van den Berg and Dichaba 2013). The key element of this learning approach/model is how the learner analyzes information obtained from real-life experience which is then reflected, evaluated, and constructed to become his/her individual knowledge (Gentry 1990; Knutson 2003; McDonald 2020). Learning needs to involve experience, both prior and/or current. However, in reality, in Indonesia, this approach/model is rarely used either in schools or in higher education institutions as proved by the lack of research or studies related to the implementation of this learning approach/model. In previous studies, a real-life experience-based learning approach/model was commonly found in language learning, especially writing or speaking classes (Nasser 2018; Kinberg 2020; Abuhassna et al. 2021), yet this learning approach remains rarely found in other subjects, such as art classes. However, in fact, information obtained from real-life experiences is necessary for art students because they need information and knowledge from real events. This is because, in art learning, students are required to be able to create work that can fulfill/meet the needs of customers (Marshal and D'Adamo 2011; Broome 2013). Hence, these conditions served as the gap that should be filled because it can affect arts learning in formal institutions. Therefore, this study aims to see how a real-life experience-based learning approach can be implemented as a learning approach in art class management as a manifestation of the freedom of learning. However, this study has several limitations, in terms of population selection, research duration, research methods, data collection techniques, and the selection of variables used. The existence of these limitations allows this study to draw different results once these limitations are included as factors discussed. Therefore, it is highly recommended to conduct further studies by including the excluded factors found in this study. Even so, this study had implications for policymakers in educational institutions, especially related to art learning activities both in schools and tertiary institutions, especially in choosing learning strategies and approaches, namely by using real experience (using real practitioners) as informants or sources. information in teaching and learning activities.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Classroom Management For Arts Study*

Classroom management is very important in the learning process. Classroom management refers to the way how teachers regulate the class conducive to achieve the goals set through interactions among the elements in the class (Watkins 2008). Meanwhile, Wiyani (2013) stated that classroom management is a way of handling or managing all activities that occur during the

learning process. In classroom management, management of student and teacher behavior, as well as management of facilities that support learning activities in class become inseparable (Rukmana & Suryana 2006; Suryana 2006; Handayani 2013). In the classroom management system, teachers have an important role especially in determining the success and effectiveness of classroom management (Mephram 2015; Broome 2013) because they own the power to organize, design, and determine the strategies, methods, as well as approaches used in classroom learning (Badamas 2021). When classroom management is carried out effectively, teachers can minimize good learning behavior so that they can optimize learning success (Özen & Yildirim 2020). Moreover, classroom management has the greatest effect on student achievement (Schroeder 2010; Mansor et al. 2012; Parsonson 2012). Thus, it is necessary to design and set a good management system in order to create optimal conditions for learning activities (Oliver, Wehby, & Reschly 2011; Mudianingrum, Evenddy, & Rima 2019; Roohi, Qureshi, & Butt 2022). There were many studies conducted on classroom management previously, yet most of them focused on how to manage the subjects of the classroom such as students or teachers (Goodenow 1993; Wentzel 2003). However, they rarely discussed the objects used to manage the class such as the learning approach or strategy. Accordingly, this research attempted to discuss the appropriate learning approach to manage the class. The reason on why this focus was brought was due to the consideration of the selection of the class that was used in this study. A class for art study is fairly different compared to general classes because, in this type of class, the goal of the learning process is not only to deliver learning material theoretically but also practically (Marshal & D'Adamo 2011; Broome 2013; Mephram 2015). Referring to these opinions, the researcher defines class management in art class as a way to manage existing elements of the class including students, materials, and learning strategies in order to achieve the specified target, namely creating theoretical and practical understanding in art students related to the material taught.

B. Real-Life Experience Learning Approach

Learning experience shapes and significantly impacts the learners because it possibly affects their experience (van den Berg & Dichaba 2013). Using experiences as a learning method/approach was actually referred to as transformational learning raised by (Mezirow 1997) which was proposed by Kolb and Kolb (2017) who regarded the real-life experience as a source of knowledge. Real-life experience-based learning is a form of learning in education that focuses on individual learning processes and concerns the development of student's abilities to gain knowledge (van den Berg & Dichaba 2013; Noobanjong and Louhapensang 2017; Kinberg 2020). This learning approach refers to theories and methods that emphasize learning through action. According to (Sánchez 2011), real-life experience-based learning is learning that combines individual knowledge, skills, and attitudes and was constructed by social interactions (Postareff, Lindblom-Ylänne, & Nevgi 2008). The distinguishing feature of real-life experience-based learning was that the learner's experience occupies a central place in teaching and learning. These experiences can consist of previous events that can be used as references and information for the learner to gain new knowledge (van den Berg and Dichaba 2013; Erselcan 2015; Kolb & Kolb 2017; Abuhassna et al. 2021). A key element of experience-based learning is on how learners analyze the experiences by reflecting on, evaluating, and reconstructing them to derive meaning from them based on previous experience (Andresen, Boud, & Cohen 1995). Considering previous studies, experience-based learning was mostly discussed from the point of view of learners' experience. However, in this study, the researchers used other people's experiences (practitioners) as the bases for the learning approach

C. Freedom in Learning

Democracy is a philosophical concept that is an integral part of people's lives, not only in the realm of politics but also in education (Jamagh, Al-Muttalabi, and Samari 2021; Abuhassna et al. 2021). Educational institutions have an important role in forming and developing the concept of democracy in society (Dewey 1997; Dewey 2015; Servet & Fatih 2019; Roohi, Qureshi, & Butt 2022). Consequently, these institutions have an obligation to provide access and stimuli to their students to form this concept of thinking. Descriptively, democracy in the world of education means freedom to develop ideas and thoughts based on individual intentions, preferences, and interests in a particular knowledge or information (Carter Andrews, Richmond, & Floden 2018; Roohi, Qureshi, & Butt 2022). So, democracy in education can also be interpreted as freedom in learning. According to Carter Andrews et al. (2018), democracy in learning will create an ideal learning situation in the classroom that 1) inspires thought, 2) confronts authority, 3) stimulates the logic of competence, 4) creates a feeling of belonging, 5) encourages usability responsiveness a person, 6) provide pleasure, and 7) generate creativity, awareness of rights, and justice. So this idea will give rise to a pedagogy that will develop the freedom to think and acquire knowledge in learning which is created through interactions between elements in the class (Servet and Fatih 2019).

The freedom of learning policy refers to the idea of freedom of thought, where the teacher becomes the actor who regulates the course of the activity (Osman 2013; Lomotey 2021). This opinion provides breadth for teachers to develop their competencies without being limited by administrative signs that confine freedom in carrying out learning activities, bearing in mind that each teacher faces different students with different problems (Ozer 2013; Akçay & Üzümlü 2016; Mujtahidin, Oktarianto, & Afriyadi 2021). The free learning paradigm was initiated by Paulo Freire (Prentki & Preston 2013) which refers to (Dewey 2015) pattern of thinking about democracy in education. Freire (2005) offers a free education model which must make students creative, creative, and innovative. School is an organization or institution that facilitates learning so they must protect their environment from disturbing influences (Noobanjong & Louhapensang 2017; Roohi, Qureshi, & Butt 2022). While the learning process becomes a way that not only aims to transfer information and knowledge but also as a medium for growing intellectual, critical thinking skills, and student creativity (Nilson et al. 2013; Broome 2013). Referring to this understanding, independence in learning in this study is intended as a method used to carry out learning activities that give freedom to students (especially art students) to choose their own way of learning based on real events (experiences) experienced by the presenters of the material (teacher or relevant practitioner).

III. METHOD

This study was qualitative research in which the results of the analysis were explained by using a descriptive approach. The data for this study were obtained from 4 lecturers who taught art classes, in the Department of Arts, Drama, Dance, and Music Education at Universitas Negeri Surabaya and 85 university students who programmed art class management courses in this department. Four lecturers acted as the subjects studied because they were observed and interviewed regarding the way they managed the class that implemented a real-life experience as a learning approach. Meanwhile, the data from the 85 students were taken from the results of the midterm exam scores. These data were used to see the impact of implementing the real-life experience approach during learning activities (6 class meetings). Data from the subject were collected through observations using closed questions and scored using the measurement standard adapted from Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2013) and Miles and Huberman (1994) on how to manage and measure the data from qualitative research (see Table 1). While the results of the midterm exams from students were analyzed using 4 standard Likert scales to categorize these results, namely values 0-30 (score 1), 31-60 (score 2), 61-70 (score 3), and 71-100 (score 4). In addition, the standard limit score for student achievement (≥ 65) was also applied to see whether the approach and classroom management implemented were provably effective or not. The category regarding the student’s achievement referred to the standard set by the higher education curriculum for university students which was described in the Decree of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia Number 56/M/2022 on Curriculum Implementation Guidelines in the Framework of Teaching-Learning Recovery After Pandemic Covid—19.

Table 1. Instruments for Classroom Management.

Focus	Individual Assistance (IA)	Classroom Effect (CE)
Class Administration (CA)	1. facilitating schedules	1. relieving pressures
	2. controlling reliability	2. easing classroom arrangement
	3. solving problems	3. controlling expected problems
Teachers (T)	1. providing materials	1. reducing effort
	2. demonstrating models	2. increasing repertoire
	3. answering/responding to requests/questions	3. increasing problem-solving
	4. encouraging student’s activeness	4. maintaining level of effort
	5. controlling classroom flow	5. ambivalent: helped yet coerced
Students (A)	1. increasing self-reliance	1. encouraging individual competition
	2. decreasing complaints on learning activities	2. encouraging self-independence in solving problems
	3. improving individual confidence	3. expanding self-repertoire
	4. encouraging independent learning	4. increasing classroom activeness

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Result

From data processing, the results show that the implication of a real-life experience-based approach can assist lecturers to improve the quality of classroom management. This can be seen from the data which prove that the average result of each instrument used to assess the performance of teachers in classroom management that implemented a real-life experience-based approach is considered good (with the lowest score being 3.00 and the highest being 3.75) according to the standards set by the curriculum of higher education (see Table 2). In addition, the results of the midterm score data show that 2.4% of students failed to obtain a passing standard (score < 30) and 44.7% had not succeeded in passing the specified standard (score < 65). Whereas, the students who successfully passed the standard score set (score > 65) were 52.9%. However, from the analysis of the data obtained, only 7.0% of students obtained very satisfactory results (score > 80) indicating that the implementation of a real-life experience-based approach in art class management in higher education has a positive effect but not significant (which proved by the fact that there were many students who have not reached the passing standard score) (see Table 3). These results are possible due to the limitations imposed on this study (existing exceptions). Furthermore, these results implied that using real-life experience as learning approach can encourage individual to do independent study which means supporting the freedom of learning where each individual was responsible to their own learning improvement because teachers only provide information and facilities from the real-life situation, while the result of the improvement highly depends on individual acceptance as well as participation in learning activity.

Table 2. Classroom Management Analysis.

Items	IA			CE		
	Total	Ave	Category	Total	Ave	Category
CA.1	13	3.25	Good	13	3.25	Good
CA.2	14	3.50	Good	14	3.50	Good
CA.3	12	3.00	Good	14	3.50	Good
T.1	15	3.75	Good	14	3.50	Good
T.2	15	3.75	Good	14	3.50	Good
T.3	14	3.50	Good	15	3.75	Good
T.4	12	3.00	Good	15	3.75	Good
T.5	14	3.50	Good	15	3.75	Good
S.1	12	3.00	Good	14	3.50	Good
S.2	12	3.00	Good	12	3.00	Good
S.3	13	3.25	Good	12	3.00	Good
S.4	13	3.25	Good	12	3.00	Good

Table 3. Midterm Result Analysis.

Group	Number of students	Score				Passing Standard							
		0-30	31-60	61-70	71-100	≤ 30	< 65	65-80	> 80				
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
A	17	0	5	10	2	0	0.0	7	41.2	9	52.9	1	5.9
B	28	0	10	13	5	0	0.0	15	53.6	11	39.3	2	7.1
C	22	1	2	11	8	1	4.5	8	36.4	11	50.0	2	9.1
D	18	1	3	10	4	1	5.6	8	44.4	8	44.4	1	5.6
Total	85	2	20	44	19	2	2.4	38	44.7	39	45.9	6	7.0

B. Discussion

Classroom management is an important part of a learning system because good classroom management will increase the success of learning. This opinion is proven by previous studies about the role and influence of classroom management on learning success.

There are various elements in classroom management, judging from the side of actors (teachers and students) as well as devices (learning approach, media, strategy, methods) (Goodenow 1993; Rukmana & Suryana 2006; Meiers 2008; Schroeder 2010). Prior studies found a close relationship between the teacher as class manager and the formation of learning tools used to control the class (Goodenow 1993; Yamin & Maisah 2009; Parsonson 2012; Zein 2018). One of learning aids is learning approaches used in teaching and learning activities (Yamin & Maisah 2009; Rukmana & Suryana 2006). The approach of using real-life experience as the basis for carrying out activities is a form of learning approach that incorporates experiences from real life into pedagogy (Eisenman, Edwards, & Cushman 2015). This approach makes the experience of a person as a source of information that is used to increase the knowledge of students (Parsonson 2012; Mephram 2015). Previous studies have proved that this approach is suitable to be applied to practical learning, where students need to carry out real practice of the theory being studied (Oliver, Wehby, & Reschly 2011; Ferry et al. 2012; Oliver & Reschly 2007; Broome 2013). Kinberg (2020) mentions the importance of inviting genuine practitioners in the field of writing to teach students (academic writing) in preparing or writing scientific papers. In addition, these findings also support the writings of Noobanjong and Louhapensang (2017) and van den Berg and Dichaba (2013) who mention the importance of real experience from the teacher/material provider as a reference in preparing learning materials that refer directly to the problems students will face.

There are a lot of disciplines that require comprehension gained from experiences, one of them is arts education. In arts education, experiences obtained by arts practitioners (artists or art managers) served as the source of information that is very crucial for students in the understanding of knowledge (Marshal & D'Adamo 2011). It is because practitioners faced real problems which sometimes differed from theoretical knowledge gained from books (Mephram 2015). Arts are the result of human creations that appear as a response to one's thoughts and understanding of events that occur around them (Nelson et al. 2018). Arts practitioners carry out these artistic activities not only based on individual imagination or information obtained from books but also based on the problems faced in reality (Nilson, Fetherston, & McMurray 2014; Nelson et al. 2018). Thus, when art practitioners become teachers and provide knowledge as well as information obtained from real issues they experienced, this information and knowledge deepened learners' understanding of the knowledge conveyed (Marshal & D'Adamo 2011). The application of real experience as a form of learning approach allows students to be able to choose and organize the information they want to obtain as well as a form of teacher freedom in selecting learning systems which of course becomes an overview for the implementation of the freedom of learning. This statement is in line with the idea of Ozer (2013), Forte (2009), as well as Mujtahidin, Oktariantio, and Afriyadi (2021) who explain that freedom of learning is a form of independency that is obtained by educational actors in determining the learning system according to individuals (subjects') needs and learning targets that were previously set.

Based on these studies, this study proved there was a correlation between good classroom management by using appropriate learning approaches and the increase in students' knowledge of related material as well as the success of learning. This is proved by the analysis of the midterm exam scores which show that more than 50% of students scored above 60 (44 students scored 61-70 and 19 students scored 71-100). This standard (60) was in accordance with the provisions set by the Ministry of Research, Technology, and Higher Education regarding curriculum in higher education. However, according to the passing grade standard determined by the relevant higher institution that served as the research location (Universitas Negeri Surabaya), the passing mark is 65. Even with this mark, the results of data analysis from the midterm exams show that 52.9% of students scored above 65 (see Table 5) meaning that it was more than half (50%). These results indicated that implementing real-life experience for art classes as a learning approach is considered appropriately done. In addition, the result analysis of classroom management using 2 variables and 12 Instruments shows that all Instruments for the variables used show good results, both in terms of their correlation as assistants in the learning process and the effects they have on creating a learning atmosphere and class control. However, from the results of data processing, this study showed a result which indicated the students who were still unable to obtain good results from implementing this learning approach, proved by the 2 students who scored 0-30 (< 30) meaning that they failed to understand the material presented. However, the existence of this result was highly probably due to the excluded factors in the study.

V. CONCLUSION

Considering the results obtained in this study, the researcher recommends conducting further research especially by addressing all the excluded factors that appear in this study. In addition, studies that include government policies can be used as material for consideration to be used as other studies to determine further understanding of the results obtained in this study. Apart from these

recommendations, this research has implications for the government in general, especially as a material for consideration before designing education policies and education practitioners in choosing the right strategy for teaching and learning activities, especially learning arts both at tertiary institutions and at the school level.

Even though the results of this study have good implications, the limitations applied in this study allow for differences in the final results of the research which can support or contradict the results of this study. The limitations include internal factors and external factors that appear in the subjects and objects studied. Internal factors in research subjects are visible from the psychological and emotional background of individuals, such as: self-efficacy, self-knowledge, self-awareness, motivation, etc. While the external background that exists in research subjects includes institutional support, government policies, facilities, etc. In addition, the limited population and duration of research (observation) can affect the final results obtained. Limitations that exist in the object (learning classes using a student-centered approach) can also be seen from the criteria for the class chosen (where the researcher does not apply special prerequisites for the class chosen, thus allowing for heterogeneity of the students in the class). Therefore, the limitations found in this study require further research that discusses and examines the factors that

From the results and discussions conducted, it can be concluded in this study that the implementation of a real-life experience-based approach in managing arts management classes in higher education showed a positive effect but not a significant one. This can be seen from the results of data analysis for the implementation of classroom management which categorized good on all instruments with an average score between 3.00 to 3.75. In addition to the results of midterm score data analysis, it showed that 52.9% of students succeeded in achieving a score above the passing mark (> 65), but the remaining 47.1% failed to obtain a passing standard score (< 65). Even more, 2.4% of them were considered failed. The existence of a score below 65 more than 40% was an indication that the implementation of the real-life experience-based approach was not significant in improving students' results. Yet, it was provably able to be used as a learning approach because it showed a good category for classroom management. These differed results were due to the possibility of influence from other factors that were not included as variables in this study. Additionally, these results indirectly explained that implementing real-life experience as learning approach can encourage individual to do independent study which means supporting the freedom of learning where each person was in charge to their individual learning development because teachers/lecturers only serve as an assistance who provides information and facilities from the real-life situation, while the result of the development highly depends on individual acceptance as well as participation in learning activity.

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